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Assessment of Contrapositive Behavior Towards Physical Activity Among Obese Adolescent Girl Students in Dhaka city, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – Obese adolescent girls have determined the expanded danger for cardio-metabolic problems, such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, insulin opposition, depression, social anxiety, anger, feeling dismissed by peers, or seeing themselves as casualties' nicknames, prejudices, or hostile jokes from them peers. By now, it is a proven fact that unhealthy eating practices and non-participant in physical activity are the significant reasons for obesity worldwide. Considerable research gap has been found left to examine the intention of contrapositive behavior towards physical activity among obese adolescent girl students in Dhaka, Bangladesh. This research aims to uncover a gap by looking into the intention of obese adolescent girl students, in Dhaka city Bangladesh for contrapositive behavior towards physical activity.

Design/methodology/approach – A survey was carried out in Dhaka, Bangladesh, where the participants were 384 obese adolescent girl students from different schools, and colleges. SMART PLS-SEM- 3.0 programming were used for analyzing the information gathered from the survey.

Findings – The investigation has uncovered that attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavior control emphatically influence obese adolescent girl students in Dhaka, Bangladesh, for intention towards contrapositive behavior to physical activities.

Originality/value – Although plenty of studies had been executed into the sector of adolescent's obesity and its causes to control issues around the globe. However, plenty of research area is still found uncovered to address. Therefore, this study tried to contribute by exploring the intention of obese adolescent girl students, in Dhaka city Bangladesh for grabbing contrapositive behavior towards physical activity.

Keywords

Contrapositive Behavior, Physical Inactivity, Obese Adolescent Girl Students, The Theory Of Planned Behavior, Smart PLS-SEM-3.0

Introduction

Worldwide, overweight and heaviness among adolescents, specifically among adolescent girls (13 to 19) years, are significant general medical problems [Biswas et al 2017](#). Overabundance muscle to fat ratio during adolescence adds to more prominent health danger in puberty and adulthood, especially in childbearing years, when overabundance weight can prompt poor pregnancy results [Todd et al 2015](#). In Bangladesh, there are 27.7 million obese adolescents between the age of 10-19 years. Among them 13.7 million are girls [Hossain and Luies 2017](#). Obese adolescent girls have determined the expanded danger for the event of cardio-metabolic problems, for example, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and insulin opposition [Rahman et al 2014](#), depression [Esposito et al 2014](#), social anxiety, anger, feel not welcome by friends by getting hurt from their cruel jokes for their physical appearance that in result negatively influences their self-confidence, prompting mental unhappiness and the dodging of routine exercises and social association, for example, going to class, rehearsing a few games, having a good time, purchasing garments, and dating [Sapienza et al 2017](#) and not last but least victims of sexual harassment [Nahar et al 2013](#).

Treatment of obesity is multiplex and expensive and can include numerous weight-controlling mechanisms comprising behavioral, meditative, and surgical involvements [Todd et al 2015a](#). By now, it is a fact that unhealthy eating practices and non-participant in physical activity are the significant reasons for obesity in general around the globe [Yousif et al 2019](#). Though practicing a healthful style of living behaviors, for example, physical effort and exercise, alongside healthy dietary decisions, could alter obesity chance and improve people's health. Plenty of research has been conducted to track factors influencing obese adolescent girls to intake unhealthy foods and identify activities they are in practice [Biswas et al 2017a](#). However, identifying the weight managing behavior of obese in general also deserves attention as this would help the well-being of obese patients and families [Maytapattana 2014](#). A recent investigation unveiled that 4 out of 5 obese adolescent

girls in Dhaka city, Bangladesh, do not comply with the World Health Organization (WHO) propositions of the minimum 2.5 hours each workweek of light to vigorous physical activity (MVPA). The study also appealed to conduct further research to search for the elements that may motivate obese adolescent girls' intention for not being involved in physical activities in Dhaka city, Bangladesh [Uddin et al 2017](#).

Therefore, this paper examined the intention of contrapositive behavior to physical activity among obese adolescent girl students in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The result from this exploration will deliver a structure to figure out how to prevent and control obesity among adolescent girl students so the nation would get mentally and physically fit female citizens as workforce and as mothers who would contribute to the socio-economic development now and in the future.

Literature Review

The literature reviews also confirmed a lack of studies that tried to explore the intention of contrapositive behavior towards physical activity among obese adolescent girl students at home and abroad. Nearly all previous literature spotlighted healthy eating customs and physically active behaviors as the prime basis for preventing and controlling adolescent girls' obesity. Few to refer, from the investigation of [Musaigeret al 2016](#) healthy nutritional habits and robust behaviors, control of consumption of junk food, fast food, and fried food, according to [Al-Mamun et al 2019](#), being physically active rather than spending too much time in front of the TV screen or a computer monitor, playing video games, browsing the Internet and mobile phones as per [Yeasminet al 2015](#), physical involvement rather than sleeping or gossiping during leisure time as per [Lahiriet al 2019](#).

Materials and methods

Hypothetical Framework

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) has gotten one of the most tediously referenced and driving models for forecasting human social behavior all around [Suchaet al 2014](#). This way, this theory has been viewed as utilized for this examination. This theory was introduced in 1985 and finalized in 1991 by Ajzen and

Fishbein. As demonstrated by this principle, the most important cause of the behavior is the will to take an interest in a conduct. Like this, the intention is molded by mentality or attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. Attitude implies a tendency or responding empathically or absurdly to someone or something. It is made out of feelings and assessments of social outcomes. The subjective norm is represented as seen social pressure that people feel to perform conduct. It is made out of regulating faith and motivation to consent. The perceived behavioral control suggests people's feelings about the particular conduct's straightforwardness or inconvenience [Taperaet al 2020](#).

The Model

Given the speculative structure, an exploration model is created to clarify this examination's principal ideas, introduced in Figure 1.

Figure 1: *The model that was created for research dependent on the TPB.*

[Ajzen 1991](#)

Procedures

For the model's assessment, a survey was carried out in Dhaka, Bangladesh, where the participants were 384 obese adolescent girl students from different schools, and colleges [Sarkar and Hossain 2016](#). The convenience sampling method was used to

select the sample frame [Batson 2014](#). The sampling technique for this study was purposive sampling. For the respondents ease to understand the questionnaire and to answer them correctly and easily, the modified version of the questionnaire was converted into the "Bangla" linguistic. It was assessed on five points Likert scale [Behr 2018](#). For quantifying the model of TPB, a questionnaire was developed by reviewing the previous works of [Armstrong et al 2018](#), [Kayani et al 2018](#), [Lee and Moudon 2004](#). Before direct the investigation, consent was taken from the school and college authorities over the phone to meet with them first and expose our identity, explaining to them the research objectives. Upon their satisfaction, a date was fixed to conduct the survey [Strugnellet al 2018](#). On the specific day, the researchers and 6 female research assistants went to the schools and colleges, met the authorities, proceeded to the classrooms with the representative from the authority's side, explained the faculty was present in the classroom the purpose of the study. Before distributing questionnaires, the students were informed of the study's purpose, its process, and only those who gave their consent to participate in the survey; body mass index was determined using the formula, $BMI = \text{weight (kg)} / (\text{height(m)}^2)$. Body height was measured as the distance from the top of the head in the midsagittal plane to the floor, and it was estimated by stadiometer without shoes to the adjacent 0.1 cm. Bodyweight was recorded while wearing clothing and without shoes utilizing a portable Digital Display Height and Weight measurement Machin, to the nearest 0.1kg. Only the participants ($BMI \geq 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$) were given the questionnaire to receive their feedback [Rahman et al 2016](#) as obesity is characterized as the presence of a body mass index ($BMI \geq 30$) [Alasmari et al 2017](#). The students were also assured that the information from the study should be used only for research purposes [Luadlailiet al 2018](#).

Data Analysis

SMART PLS-SEM- 3.0 programming were used for analyzing the information gathered from the survey. This program has been used to analyze data for much

prominent research around the world [Javed et al 2020](#) few to refer, [Khoi and Van Tuan 2018](#), [Hussain and Endut 2018](#), [Shiau and Liu 2019](#), [Busu and Busu 2021](#), [Dewiet et al 2019](#). The legitimacy of the reflective model is tried through Cronbach's alpha (CA), Composite reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). A reliability test to be assessed is pretty high and satisfactory by the greater part of the principles when the Cronbach's alpha is 0.70 and higher [Inalet et al 2017](#). Composite reliability quality was also coordinated to evaluate the hidden data pieces' internal reliability. Composite reliability is a more notable measure of reliability since Cronbach's alpha sometimes miscarry the scale reliability. CR valuations somewhere in the range of 0.60 and 0.70 are considered "adequate in exploratory research," values somewhere in the range of 0.70 and 0.90 territories from "agreeable to great." [Hair et al 2019](#). After; along these lines, the convergent rationality was calculated by determining Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. AVE values starting from 0.50 to higher demonstrating that the concept clarifies in any event 50% of the fluctuation of its items [Hair et al 2019a](#). Table 1 demonstrates that the value of Cronbach's alpha (CA), Composite reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) records for this research is well within the proposed boundaries.

Table I: *The gathered data from the survey and the analysis*

Indicators	Description	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's alpha (CA)	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ATT			0.89	0.92	0.68
ATT1	The student denies walking due to the lack of parks.	0.86			
ATT2	The student denies cycling due to traffic congestion.	0.82			
ATT3	The student denies aerobics due to a lack of facilities.	0.86			

ATT4	The student denies jogging due to the poor condition of the neighborhood streets.	0.79			
ATT5	The student denies swimming due to the lack of swimming pools in the neighborhood.	0.80			
SN			0.88	0.91	0.67
SN1	The student's friends refrain her from walking due to a lack of parks.	0.85			
SN2	Most people who are essential in the student's life persuade her not to cycle due to traffic congestion.	0.84			
SN3	Other students influence her to not doing aerobics due to lack of facilities.	0.66			
SN4	The parents convince her not to go jogging due to the poor condition of the neighborhood streets.	0.88			
SN5	The student's friends refrain her from swimming due to the neighborhood's lack of swimming pools.	0.86			
PBC			0.80	0.86	0.56
PBC1	The student has complete control not to walk due to the lack of parks.	0.63			
PBC2	The student has complete control not to cycle due to traffic congestion.	0.85			
PBC3	The student has complete control not to do aerobics due to lack of facilities.	0.82			

PBC4	The student has complete control not to jog due to the poor condition of the neighborhood streets.	0.76			
PBC5	The student has complete control not to swim due to the lack of swimming pools in the neighborhood.	0.65			
INT			0.83	0.88	0.60
INT1	The student intends to deny walking due to the lack of parks in the future.	0.84			
INT2	The student intends to refrain from cycling due to traffic congestion in the future.	0.82			
INT3	The student intends to stay away from aerobics due to a lack of facilities in the future.	0.84			
INT4	The student intends not to jog due to the poor condition of the neighborhood streets in the future.	0.75			
INT5	The student intends not to swim due to the lack of swimming pools in the neighborhood in the future.	0.61			
BEH			0.78	0.85	0.54
BEH1	The student has denied walking due to the lack of parks in the past.	0.72			
BEH2	The student has refrained from cycling due to traffic congestion in the past.	0.83			

BEH3	The student has stayed away from aerobics due to a lack of facilities in the past.	0.69			
BEH4	The student has not jogged due to the poor condition of the neighborhood streets in the past.	0.64			
BEH5	In the past, the student had not swum due to the neighborhood's lack of swimming pools.	0.78			

Results

The investigation has uncovered that attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavior control emphatically influence obese adolescent girl students in Dhaka, Bangladesh, for intention towards contrapositive behavior to physical activities. Accordingly, to address those components, the concerned authority's conspicuous decision should limit traffic congestion, create parks, improve the local roads, build swimming pools and create facilities where obese adolescent girls in Dhaka can perform physical activities. Nonetheless, the cruel truth is that Dhaka has an enormous land shortage and has a weight populace of around 17 million. In this way, infrastructure advancement is not generally the possible responses for serving the occupants' needs in Dhaka city, Bangladesh. Hence, concerned connoisseurs in Dhaka, Bangladesh, may think about beginning instruction and preparing programs for obese adolescent girl students, controlling obesity by publicizing programs through billboards, and different sorts of advertising vehicles, such as radio and TV, newspapers, and in particular, through web-based media. E.g., Facebook featuring points of interest of utilizing indoor physical activity fitness tools, for example, indoor cycle, trade mill, jumping rope, organizing online classes on classical dance, exercise and yoga, rooftop walking and running, and in particular to spread the message to be active on household chores, for example, mopping the floor, washing their own clothes and above all to climb stairs instead of utilizing lifts. Notwithstanding, the publicizing exercises must incorporate the alert for obese adolescent girl students to have their physical condition checked by doctors before engaging in psychical action.

Conclusion

Obesity among adolescent girl students in Dhaka, Bangladesh, is gradually on the climb today and will keep on rising in the future with severe medical problems, which will definitely hinder Bangladesh's socio-economic progress. Therefore, serious government involvement will be expected to take necessary action to lessen the concern and its related medical negativity to make optimistic and prosperous Bangladesh.

Ethical Declaration

The research team members sincerely practiced the norms of the ethical policy prescribed by the Bangladesh Medical Research Council (BMRC), so the physical risks social risks, psychological risks, discomfort to subjects, invasion of the body, invasion of privacy, disclosure of information damaging to subject or others were safeguarded while conducting the research [BMRC, 2020](#).

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